

Oncotype DX Recurrence Score in HER2-Negative, ER/PR-Positive Breast Cancer: A Preliminary Study and the First Iraqi Experience

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Abstract

Introduction: The Oncotype DX recurrence score (RS) is a key determinant in guiding chemotherapy decisions for hormone receptor-positive, HER2-negative breast cancer patients. This study examines RS distribution, its correlation with clinical variables, and its impact on treatment recommendations in an Iraqi cohort. **Methods:** a total of 383 patients with classified in to tow age group <50 years (107) and ≥ 50 years (276), mean, and Standard deviations were calculated for each age group. An independent samples t-test and chi square test was used test if there was significant difference in mean of RS between these independent groups <50 vs. ≥ 50 years. **Results:** A retrospective cohort analysis was conducted using patient records from oncology clinics. Patients were stratified into two age groups (<50 and ≥ 50), and Recurrence Scores (RS) were classified into low (0–10), intermediate (11–25), and high (≥ 26) categories. Statistical analyses included descriptive statistics, **Conclusion:** RS plays a critical role in chemotherapy decision-making for HER2-negative, ER/PR-positive breast cancer. Younger patients demonstrate higher recurrence scores, underscoring the need for personalized treatment strategies in Iraq. These findings contribute to regional oncology research by refining recurrence risk assessments and supporting evidence-based precision medicine approaches.

Introduction

Breast cancer is still the most common type of cancer and the second most common cause of cancer deaths throughout the world. The rates of breast cancer and the success of treatments vary greatly from one location to the next [1]. In Iraq, it is the most often diagnosed cancer in women, which shows how important it is to have good predictive tools to help doctors make treatment decisions and improve outcomes [2]. The Oncotype DX recurrence score (RS) is a well-established genetic test utilised to evaluate the recurrence risk in individuals with hormone receptor-positive, HER2-negative breast cancer. It also helps figure out how probable it is that adding chemotherapy to endocrine treatment would help [3,4]. Clinical studies like TAILORx and NSABP B-20 have demonstrated that chemotherapy works well for people with high RS values (≥ 26), but it may not work

as well for those with intermediate scores (11–25) [4]. Molecular profiling advancements have revolutionised breast cancer treatment by facilitating personalised strategies that reduce superfluous chemotherapy while guaranteeing effective care for high-risk patients [5,6]. there is a paucity of evidence about the distribution and clinical significance of Oncotype DX scores in the Middle East, especially in Iraq. Oncotype DX is used in several Arab countries mostly in private centers. The significance of region-specific evidence is underscored by disparities in healthcare infrastructure, therapeutic accessibility, and genetic variation [7,8]. This study seeks to report on Oncotype DX RS in Iraqi patients with HER2-negative, ER/PR-positive breast cancer.

Material and Methods

This retrospective cohort study investigates the relationship between Oncotype DX recurrence scores (RS) and chemotherapy recommendations in Iraqi

More Information

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Keywords:

Oncotype, DX, Recurrence Score, HER2-Negative, ER/PR-Positive, Breast Cancer.

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patients with HER2-negative, ER/PR-positive breast cancer. The study specifically explores variations in RS by age and tumour size to improve individualized risk assessment.

Patient data were retrospectively collected from oncology clinics and hospital records. Eligibility criteria included confirmed HER2-negative, estrogen/progesterone receptor-positive breast cancer with available Oncotype DX testing results. A total of 383 Participants were grouped by age into two categories: those younger than 50 years and those aged 50 years or older. scores were done according to manufacture.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board (IRB), and all data were anonymized to ensure patient confidentiality in accordance with ethical research standards.

Results

Table 1: Mean and Oncotype DX Scores by Age Group

Age Group	No.	Mean	Standard Deviation
<50	107	24.43	18.11
≥50	276	20.58	13.74

Note: T= -2.24, D.F =381; P= 0.026

Table2: Tumour Size Category * Risk Classification Crosstabulation

	Risk score of HER2 -					
	high		moderate		low	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 2	40	25.8	76	48.4	39	25.2
≥ 2	74	27.7	109	40.8	84	31.5

$\chi^2 = 2.9$, D.F.=2, P=0.2

Figure 1: Correlation between PR Score and Recurrence Score

Discussion

This study highlights the clinical relevance of the Oncotype DX recurrence score (RS) in guiding chemotherapy decisions for HER2-negative breast

cancer patients in Iraq. The findings demonstrate that younger patients <50 revealed significantly higher recurrence risk (P=0.026), which might influence more aggressive treatment decisions in this group. The distribution of RS within this cohort mirrors global patterns, with the majority of patients falling within the intermediate-risk category, consistent with findings from large-scale studies such as TAILORx and RxPONDER [4,5]. This tendency is consistent with international research indicating that genetic profiling has supplementary prognostic significance beyond conventional clinical indicators [6]. In contrast, chi-square test could not establish a statistically significant correlation between tumour size and risk categorisation (p > 0.05); yet, observed patterns indicate that more inquiry may be necessary. Nonetheless, variables such as patient age and tumour size may continue to affect recurrence risk, underscoring the necessity for more study across many demographic contexts [9]. Although its efficacy has been established in Western populations, these findings highlight the complexity of recurrence risk assessment and the necessity of integrating multigene testing into treatment decision-making [10]. This underscores the increasing need for more advanced and comprehensive tools to guide treatment planning in Iraq. Although traditional clinical indicators such as tumor size, grade, lymph node status, and hormonal receptor expression remain relevant in therapeutic decision-making, their predictive value is limited when used in isolation. where treatment regimens often depend on these parameters due to resource constraints. Previous local studies have documented inconsistencies in hormone receptor testing, potentially affecting clinical outcomes [11,12]. In the absence of detailed IHC data for ER, PR, and HER2, Oncotype DX gene expression scores offered a valuable alternative for tumor characterization. Most cases showed moderate-to-high ER and PR expression, with HER2 scores remaining below the positivity threshold, supporting the accuracy of clinical classification. with an inverse relationship between PR gene expression and Recurrence Score, where lower PR levels were linked to higher scores and potentially more aggressive disease. This finding aligns with previous studies, including the ADAPT HR+/HER2- trial, and underscores the prognostic value of PR expression and the importance of genomic profiling in settings with variable IHC quality [13]. These limitations highlight the necessity for precision oncology tools, such as the Oncotype DX assay, to be integrated into routine clinical practice. As further evidence demonstrates the clinical use of Oncotype DX, it is imperative to enhance the accessibility of genetic profiling in Iraq to improve patient outcomes, mitigate overtreatment, by minimizing overtreatment in low-risk patients and

identifying patients who would benefit from chemotherapy escalation and refine chemotherapy prescriptions. Also underscores the imperative for equitable access to molecular diagnostics, particularly in resource-limited settings where treatment decisions often rely on traditional clinicopathologic criteria. Future research should examine the cost-effectiveness, survival of patients and feasibility of widespread implementation, addressing potential disparities in access to precision oncology tools [2,8].

Conclusion

This study underscores the gradual but systematic adoption of Oncotype DX in tailoring chemotherapy options for Iraqi breast cancer patients. Such a shift would represent a meaningful step toward personalized medicine, reducing unnecessary chemotherapy and improving patient's outcome in accordance with the latest international standards.

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